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(ICRTB 2024)

January 19-20, 2024

ABSTRACTS

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Screening of potential Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR) for agrochemical nutrient enhancement

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Abstract: The properties of *Azadirachta indica*, known for its bioactive compounds with pesticidal and antimicrobial properties, render it an intriguing source for bacteria with potential agroecological benefits. This study systematically investigates the suitability of rhizospheric bacteria sourced from *Azadirachta indica* (neem) for utilization as an environmentally friendly biofertilizer. After employing conventional isolation techniques, bacterial strains were rigorously assessed for their potassium and nitrogen-fixing potential application. Further, screened isolates characterized as a notable candidate thorough biochemical characterization, providing insights into its metabolic profile. The experimental phase also involves as significant potential as a biofertilizer via their application with better growth traits by studying their impact on tomato seeds. This research seeks to discern the efficacy of identified bacterial isolate as a potent biofertilizer, presenting promising avenues for the integration of sustainable agricultural practices and advancements in agribiotechnological applications.

Keywords: *Azadirachta indica*, rhizospheric bacteria, biofertilizer, nitrogen fixation, potassium fixation.

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ISBN 978-93-6039-051-8

